

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SHAPING WAYS OF THE SOCIAL SERVICE SECTOR IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Here we will mainly look at the development of the social service sphere and social work in European countries and the United States. The difficulties that arose after World War I required innovations and reforms in the field of social service, however, since there was no organization and specific program in this direction in the world, the individual policies of states could not bring about any fundamental changes in this field, and the global economic crisis that occurred in the late 1920s and then the coming to power of Nazism in Germany led to a halt in work in this field. During this period, the main changes in the field of social policy occurred in the United States, Great Britain and Germany. Unfortunately, socio-economic changes in Germany did not lead to progress in the lives of the population, and this factor also played a significant role in the orientation of the dissatisfied majority to Nazism under the leadership of Hitler. With the beginning of World War II, development in every field, not only social, but also economic, fell behind by at least 10 years. Although the Nazis were destroyed with the end of the war in 1945, it cost the victorious countries a lot. Economic resources were depleted, and the huge human losses made positive changes impossible in a short time. However, the radical changes taking place on the world political scene – the United Nations, the World Bank, and the International Monetary Fund – made it impossible to The new economic order established with the creation of the Monetary Fund later gave impetus to development in the social sphere and led to a more organized and comprehensive organization of work in this field.

Keywords: Social welfare, welfare state, social approaches, Scandinavian model, Europe.

Introduction

The emergence of new international organizations in Europe, America and Asia in the 1950s and later also made a great contribution to this issue and greatly facilitated it. These organizations (European Economic Community, Organization of American States, ASEAN, OSCE, etc.) covered both economic and social issues. The emergence of new organizations not only developed the field of social services, but also brought new methods and approaches to this field. On the other hand, the end of colonialism, along with the social awakening in the exploited states and peoples, paved the way for this field of services, because the demand for it was great. The greatest lesson that the world learned from the scourge of Nazism was that the peoples of the world should choose a new path of development based on democratic values, welfare and sound ideological foundations in order to prevent such events from happening again. In this area, the European peoples, who suffered the most, were especially active, because they understood very well that Europe would be completely destroyed in the event of a new world war. The fact that Germany, France, Great Britain and the Scandinavian countries took the social and economic spheres as pillars of state policy in the second half of the 20th century and were able to create new models in this area 20-30 years later was due to this and the historically strong traditions of solidarity and togetherness in these nations. The fact that Germany, which was defeated in 1945 and whose cities and villages were destroyed, surprised the world with its development in the 1960s and 1970s was precisely due to the fact that it abandoned militaristic policies and put the citizen at the center of all political programs. The formation of strong human capital provided the basis not only for economic

development, but also for social justice and political stability.

Methodology

Although the German and Scandinavian models in the field of social welfare were particularly successful, the pioneer in Europe in this area was Great Britain, on the other hand, historical traditions and the structure of society in Foggy Albion also made this much easier. In Britain, vulnerable groups of the population were first identified and the types of care to be provided to these individuals were determined. Such vulnerable groups included people with mental and physical disabilities, the elderly and children, offenders and victims of crime, and people with learning disabilities. To work with such population groups, territorial teams of social work departments were allocated. These teams began to provide daily care, medical and psychological support, and legal assistance to these individuals. Starting in 1948, health, social welfare, and children's departments among government agencies in Great Britain began to deal with the provision of social services. In the same year, a children's department was created under government agencies. At the end of the 1960s, these departments were merged into a single entity, under the name of the Departments of Social Work and Social Services. This, in turn, gave impetus to the formation of social work as a separate profession. Thanks to the work done, the costs allocated to daily care increased. In general, social work in the UK is handled by the ministries of education, health and family and children. Children's departments are more concerned with the education of children and the protection of them from harmful influences. The Children and Young People Act, adopted in 1969, aimed to eliminate discrimination between children and young people in cases of violence. The Children Act, adopted in 1989, tightened the

conditions for their transfer from family care to care centers.

Personalization

Personalization refers to the tailoring of social services to the needs and desires of the individual. This term is used broadly to refer to a variety of methods designed to achieve a common goal. These methods include:

Personalized assessment and response-based service

Care agreed with the client

An “indicative” personal budget managed by social workers and allocated according to the client’s needs

Direct Payments to caregivers themselves or to service users

Personalized services have been proposed to offer users greater freedom of choice, increased control over the services provided and those providing them, and improved service quality. However, there is widespread criticism of the application of personalization, mainly regarding how “personal” it is. There is mixed evidence that personal budgets do not work in some cases.

The main goal of legal support is to maintain public order, reduce criminal tendencies, ensure the punishment of criminals, and subsequently ensure their rehabilitation.

The European Social Model – Results

As the name suggests, this model covers all European countries. It was created based on the Scandinavian model, and two of the 4 social models taken as a basis in Europe are the Finnish and Swedish models. After the unification of the European space and its transformation into a political union in the 1990s, a single European model began to be established based on these 4 models. Although individual countries behave autonomously in terms of application, leading to the emergence of inevitable differences, the principles and approach are generally uniform. More precisely, the implementation of social policy here takes place at the European (Union), national and local levels. Although the European Commission determines the allocation of funds and the areas to be spent, the states themselves carry out the spending and control of the allocated funds. The Council of Europe prepares the policy and theoretical foundations, the Parliament adopts it, and the Commission controls and manages it. The main difference in the issue of social services in European countries is determined on the basis of the similarities and differences of the countries, where demography, human capital and migration issues are taken as the basis. According to the document “Social Protection” adopted by the European Commission in 2000, the relevant systems of European countries should converge on the basis of common principles, but country-specific differences hinder this standardization. On the other hand, small European countries do not want to become dependent on large countries in this matter, and relatively religious southern and western European countries are also suspicious of the approach of the more secular northern and eastern countries of the continent, and have difficulty convincing the population of this. In this

regard, 4 different social service systems can be shown in Europe:

Scandinavian model

This model, which is applied in Sweden, Denmark, Norway and Finland, is based on the principle of universalism, providing ready-made services and scholarships to children, disabled people and the elderly in the risk group on a budget basis. The main role here is played by local government agencies, the participation of NGOs in the process is not great, and other organizations - financial institutions - also partially participate. The many advantages of this model for users make it attractive. So, here:

Numerous and high-quality services

Gender sensitivity

Close attention to users’ rights and needs (open access to customer records, detailed explanation of legal and other issues, etc.)

important. However, in recent years, this model, also called the Northern model, has undergone some changes due to economic and social factors. Universalism is not easily accepted and the participation of NGOs is increasing due to the increasing policy of “welfare pluralism”.

Family care model

This model is widespread in Mediterranean countries (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece, Malta). Here, due to the historically strong influence of religion, the state provision of relevant services is limited, and the main burden of social care falls on the shoulders of the family, following the Catholic tradition. NGOs also play a second main role in this matter after the family. Among the mentioned countries, only Italy has extensive state provision. This model is strongly criticized by feminists because it is considered the main caregiver and therefore limits women’s participation in the labor market, and because there are few day care centers for young children. On the other hand, the rights of service users are not clearly explained here. This model is also referred to as the first model of social service (Lorenz: 1994). Since it depends on family care, the term “privatization” is also used in relation to it (Daly, Lewis: 2000)

Beveridge model

This model is most commonly associated with the United Kingdom and, to a lesser extent, Ireland. Here, the state withdraws from its role as a direct service provider, outsourcing this work to providers from other sectors and providing services on a “problem case” basis – targeting those with limited incomes and those most dependent on such services. Commercial organizations and NGOs play a major role here. Privatisation is applicable to this model, as commercial organisations are widely used for various purposes.

Subsidiarity model

In this model, which is dominant in Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, France and Belgium, the main work falls on the shoulders of NGOs. Churches and other religious organizations also participate to some extent in this process. The state plays a major role in financing NGOs. Families also have a great responsibility. Although it is considered a single model, there

are significant differences in its implementation between countries. In France, childcare is more of a state responsibility, while in the case of the elderly, it is the opposite, but this is not the case in other countries.

In addition, there are former communist countries of Eastern and Central Europe, for which the term fifth group is sometimes used. Some signs of the former communist system still remain in these countries, but in general they have adopted the line of the Western European welfare model. Therefore, it is difficult to attribute countries of this type to any specific model. The communist system unequivocally denied social problems, there were no NGOs in the countries, and the creation of any public and political associations was prohibited. This system presented itself as “perfect”, presenting itself as an ideal society. Social security issues were completely monopolized by the state. After 1989, with the collapse of this system, the former communist bloc countries that gained freedom faced serious and acute social problems. Economic crises became inevitable. Although some countries successfully completed the transition period that lasted more than 10 years, others still cannot get rid of the problems. Not only the legacy of the past, but also the economic, social potential, and demographic indicators of those countries play an important role here. Overall, the development strategies of Eastern and Central European countries in the 1990s and beyond placed great emphasis on international cooperation, decentralization for regional and local government, rapprochement between the state and civil society, professional training for social workers, and the development of community services.

Discussion

The social work profession promotes social change, problem solving in human relationships, and the liberation and empowerment of people in order to expand welfare services (Hare: 2004). The main question arising from this international definition of social work is to what extent social work represents change within the framework of social policy. We will try to find an answer to this question based on empirical evidence. Here we will look at the experience of several countries. First, we will turn to Norway and Estonia, the most advanced state among the Baltic countries.

Social work education existed in Estonia since the beginning of the 20th century. The Institute of Home Economics, founded in 1935, trained social workers. The course of study in this field lasted 3 years and had a widespread socio-economic orientation at that time (Kiik and Sirotkina: 2005). Since the Soviet government did not attach importance to social work, this field began to weaken in the country in the following years after the occupation of Estonia by the USSR. In 1950, the USSR closed the Institute and education and training in social work were rejected (Tulva: 1996). Since the Soviet government denied social problems, the field of social work also suffered the same fate. After Estonia regained its independence in 1991, it recognized the need for reforms in the field of social work and extensive work was carried out in this area. Relevant educational structures were restored, training of social workers began at the Universities of Tallinn and Tartu. The professional concept of social work was

adopted and in 1995 the Social Welfare Act was adopted. Local social service departments began to recruit and train social workers. In 2004, an association of social workers was established. Estonian social workers are seriously engaged in the registration and provision of benefits, paying special attention to the unemployed. Providing social benefits to the unemployed is also a sensitive issue for the state. Another important issue for social workers in Estonia is lonely people and helping them. Social workers note that the main reason for their success here is trust, the trust of local authorities in them, and the main problem is the lack of coordination between regional and local institutions. Of course, social problems cannot be solved only by local authorities and municipalities, the support of regional and sometimes national governments is also important here. In turn, social workers in this country constantly improve their knowledge and professional training, preferring to study in the practical field rather than in theory. Social workers in this country note the lack of qualified specialists and a lack of resources as the main problems.

In Norway, social work is somewhat different and is seen more as an integral part of different sectors of society. The Social Services Act and the Child Protection Act are the main documents in the field of social work in this country. These laws are directly related to the previous Social Assistance Act (1967). The need for reforms in the field of assistance to the poor was the most important factor in the formation of social work education in Norway in the 1950s. The political demand for professionals in this field presented the transformation of social work into a profession as a social democratic reform project. Norwegian social workers see their work as a social democratic welfare system (Esping-Andersen: 1990). There is a strong professional association of social workers in this country. The fact that their work consists of a specific and clear mission minimizes the interference of others in this field and helps to work more effectively. There is a wide demand for these professional skills in society, but on the other hand, the view of those engaged in this work is ambiguous and prejudiced in society. In Norway, the main providers of social services and benefits are municipalities. Social work in this country is based on the principle of “helping self-help”. Since the 1960s, social workers have become leading figures in local government (Hutchinson and Oltedal: 2006). Norwegian municipalities have considerable independence in the field of social policy, which helps them to do this work more quickly and efficiently. The rights of social service users are determined by their needs.

In local communities, great attention is paid to the protection of children. Social workers meet with people, learn about their problems and communicate them to the relevant organizations, helping to solve them. Social workers are trusted in society and in some cases, people and groups allow them to speak on their behalf. People have high expectations of social workers. When these expectations are not met, they can create tension. A trend observed in this country in recent years is the increase in the number of ethnic minority representatives among social workers. This shows that social

problems are more common among ethnic minorities (Flotten: 2001). Such problems are more evident in the field of labor (finding a job). First and second generation immigrants in particular have problems integrating into Norwegian society. Although the integration program is intended for everyone, not everyone can benefit from it for some objective and subjective reasons. On the other hand, the main trend observed by social workers in this country is the increase in people with multiple problems. This is mainly due to the young generation getting into bad habits. People who fall into depression often have difficulty getting out of it and the problems increase even more. In recent years, municipal social programs in Norway have been restructured and coordinated with state welfare programs, as poverty remains a major social problem. Although there is high specialization, support from regional and national governments is essential for solving such problems.

Finnish and Swedish model

The Finnish model places more emphasis on social work education, and educational institutions play a major role here. The university acts as a mediator between the fields of research, teaching and practice. According to the strategy set by politicians, managers control the areas of teaching and practice in this process, while separate working groups work with citizens. NGOs are actively involved in this work. The Finnish model places great importance on research in this process, treats all methods equally, promotes reflective thinking and problem-solving through dialogue. Here, the focus is more on mutual cooperation through social relations than on theory. Based on all this, and based on the great importance of the Finnish model to education, it would be useful to consider the Finnish education system. Education in Finland is universal and all citizens have the same rights to education. Literacy has been a priority in this country since the 17th century, the state aims to train highly educated, competent personnel, and after compulsory education, free formal education is offered to everyone. Local municipalities organize free lunches for students in schools with the support of the government. Although private schools are virtually non-existent in the country, private day care centers and kindergartens are widespread. Local municipalities and other state agencies have a major role in shaping educational policy and can change the curriculum if it is not appropriate for the area (Core Curriculum for Preschool Education: 2000; National Core Curriculum for Primary Education: 2004). Formal education begins after 9 years of compulsory education. Appropriate education and high performance of teachers are very important in Finland, with a bachelor's degree required for primary school teachers and a master's degree for secondary school teachers (Sahlberg: 2011). Teachers are free to choose their teaching time and method. Special attention is paid to the well-being of students. Every school has a psychologist, medical staff and social workers. After school and higher education, young people become full participants in the state's social welfare programs. In Finland, the relative difficulty in the field of social work is related to the elderly, which is common throughout the world.

Obtained results

The "Early Intervention for Families" project and its results

This project, as part of the Nordic Council of Ministers' program " *Early preventive measures for families at risk of social marginalization* ", covers the work done in this area in 2011 and 2012. The project covers 4 areas: relevant research on risk and protective factors, establishing early intervention models in the countries, ensuring easy access to relevant services for the expert group, and prioritizing children's problems.

Comprehensive support for families with children has long been a distinctive component of the Scandinavian social welfare model. Thanks to this, the birth rate in these countries is stable and relatively high. Families with children receive financial support, special attention is paid to children, and labor legislation recognizes benefits for such families. Family centers and similar activities can be seen as an example of comprehensive support for families in the Scandinavian countries. The number of such centers is increasing and is also being met with interest in other countries. Families with children are a suitable area for preventive measures. One of the main goals is to identify the needs of children in such families at an early age and help them grow up properly. This also includes adaptive and other support measures for families with different cultures. Family centers operate as a joint organization of numerous state agencies and occupy a priority position in the state's social policy. These centers, which began operating in the 2000s, are also an improved form of the reforms and models that preceded them. *The Gothenburg model* was created back in the 1970s with the same goal. The activities of these centers are supervised by municipalities and exist in all other Scandinavian countries except Iceland. The activities of the centers also aim to ensure the reintegration of children separated from their families for various reasons into the family and society, and to serve the reunification of families. Studies confirm that such centers operate successfully and are beneficial for families. Sweden is the most experienced in this field, and family centers in this country perform 4 main functions. These functions include **maternal care, child care, preschool education and social services**. In Norway, these centers cover the coordination of all simple activities and necessary services. The Finnish model, on the other hand, involves the consolidation of all services in one center. In Finland, a special education specialist is assigned to areas where there are no family centers and he or she is engaged in these activities. Here, universal, selected and individual services are distinguished. Universal services apply to all families with children, selected services cover children in the risk group. Individual services are especially relevant for vulnerable and problematic children. There is a separate program in Sweden for children whose parents have divorced, they are divided into groups and appropriate training and education is organized. As a result, it was later discovered that such a mechanism, called **Fridlyst**, has a positive impact on the socialization and future networking of these children.

Conclusion

Research and interviews show that the difficulties and maintenance of families in the present era are more difficult than in previous times, and support should be broader. Without additional support, fathers and mothers in many cases today cannot cope with their roles. This is usually more necessary during the transitional age of children. For this reason, the activities of family centers are necessary. In Sweden, there is a family program that covers support for all age groups. The program covers the period from pregnancy to adolescence. In Denmark, the **Modrehjaelpen** organization is engaged in the development of support programs for poor and needy mothers and young women, as well as the protection of women in risk groups. In the first period of activity, information is collected from relevant institutions and individuals, analyzed, and a target group is selected. In Sweden, a project called **Pinocchio** operates for this purpose, and psychiatrists are also involved in this work. The **Kvello** model in Norway also belongs to such projects and covers the period from birth to 6 years of age, and medical indicators are considered the basis. The project is managed by regional centers.

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